

THE NON-LINEAR BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE PANELS WITH
ALTERNATIVE MEMBRANE BOUNDARY CONDITIONS ON THE UNLOADED EDGES

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Introduction

The introduction of a large number of high strength and high modulus fibres and whiskers has permitted the fabrication of a new range of composite materials and their application to a wide variety of structures. The potential of these materials is only beginning to be exploited. Their introduction has led to the need to update the present technology and to apply it to the new situations arising both in material anisotropy and application areas. One particular problem which arises when composites are fabricated as plate structures using unidirectional reinforcement and subjected to uniaxial in plane loading is that of instability. The first author discussed this problem for a rectangular orthotropic plate at the last ICCM Conference (1) and further in (2), from a theoretical viewpoint and applied the results to various composite systems. In the present contribution the analysis is extended to provide a multiterm solution in the postbuckling regime and additional membrane boundary conditions on the unloaded edges are considered. Initial imperfections are also taken into account.

The analytical work is based on a semi-energy approach. The von Karman type large deflection equation, an extension of the well known equation for isotropic plates, governing the behaviour of orthotropic plates is used together with a consideration of the total potential energy of the system. The large deflection equation is used to obtain a relation between the deflection function and stress function in terms of the unknown coefficients in the assumed deflection function. These are then used in the energy expressions and the theorem of minimum total potential energy invoked to obtain a solution for the unknown coefficients.

The Boundary Conditions

The flexural boundary conditions considered are similar to those of (1). The plate shown in Figure 1 is considered to be simply supported on its loaded

Fig. 1 - Co-ordinate axes and sign convention

ends while the unloaded edges are elastically restrained against rotation to an equal or unequal degree. This permits the cases of simply supported and fully fixed edges to be taken as limiting conditions.

The membrane boundary conditions on the loaded ends are those of zero shear stress linked with a constant in plane displacement across the plate. Written mathematically these conditions become at $x = \pm a/2$

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{xy} &= 0 \\ u &= \text{constant} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

To examine the plate after buckling the displacement u is prescribed.

On the unloaded edges two membrane boundary conditions are considered. In the first case they are stress free and hence permitted to wave in the plane of the plate. Hence at $y = 0$ and b

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{xy} &= 0 \\ \sigma_y &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In the second case the displacement in the y direction is assumed constant i.e. $\partial v / \partial x = 0$ while the total net force is zero. The shear stress is again assumed to be zero and hence at $y = 0$ and b

$$v = \text{constant}$$

$$P_y = h \int_{-a/2}^{a/2} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} dx = 0$$

$$\tau_{xy} = 0 \quad (3)$$

The first two conditions in equation (3) are related since if the net force is zero this determines the value of the constant. Alternatively, if the value of the constant is zero then a net force is necessary to hold the plate in place and prevent any displacement in the y direction.

Equation (3) can be rewritten in terms of the stress function and deflection as

$$v = \int \left(\frac{1}{E_{22}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} - \nu_{21} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right) dy = \text{constant}$$

$$P_y = h \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial x} \Big|_{a/2} - \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} \Big|_{-a/2} \right) = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Method of Analysis

The deflection function is chosen in a manner similar to that indicated in (1) as

$$w = \sum_{n=1}^N A_n Y_n \cos \frac{\pi x}{eb} \quad (5)$$

The coefficient A_n by which each algebraic function Y_n is multiplied governs the magnitude of the deflection occurring in the plate. The relationship between the deflection function and the stress function F can be obtained by using the large deflection equation of the von Karman type based on compatibility considerations, but also involving the constitutive relation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{E_{22}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^4} + H \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{1}{E_{11}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial y^4} \\ = \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Substituting for w it is found that the stress function can be taken in the form

$$F = F_1(y) + F_2(y) \cos \frac{2\pi x}{eb} \quad (7)$$

where

$$F_1'' = \frac{E_{11}\pi^2}{2e^2b^2} \frac{y^2}{2} + By + C \quad (8)$$

with B and C constants found from the membrane boundary conditions on the loaded ends F_1 is thus common for both membrane conditions on the unloaded edges.

Also F_2 is given by

$$F_2 = \frac{\pi^2}{2e^2b^4} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N A_n A_m \phi_{mn}(y) \quad (9)$$

where for the class of materials dealt with here (see (1))

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{mn} = & \sum_{s=0}^{2(r-1)} L_{smn} \left(\frac{y}{b}\right)^s + C_{1mn} \cosh k_1 y + C_{2mn} \sinh k_1 y \\ & + C_{3mn} \cosh k_2 y + C_{4mn} \sinh k_2 y \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The values of the four constants $C_{1mn} - C_{4mn}$ can be obtained by considering the membrane boundary conditions on the unloaded edges. Applying equation (2) gives on the edges $y = 0$ and $y = b$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{mn}' &= 0 \\ \theta_{mn} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

This leads to a series of four equations from which the values of the four constants can be evaluated. The details for this boundary condition are given in (1).

For the second membrane boundary condition where the displacement in the y direction is held constant the values of the constants are found by satisfying equation (4). The zero shear stress condition is satisfied by taking on the edges $y = 0$ and $y = b$

$$\phi_{mn}' = 0 \quad (12)$$

The constant displacement condition is met by substituting for F and w in the expression for v . This leads to the expression

$$v = \int \left(\frac{1}{E_{22}} \left(-\frac{4\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} F_2 \cos \frac{2\pi x}{eb} - v_{21} (F_1'' + F_2'' \cos \frac{2\pi x}{eb}) \right) - \frac{1}{2} (y')^2 \cos^2 \frac{2\pi x}{eb} \right) dy \quad (13)$$

This can be separated into 2 parts as

$$v = \int \left(-\frac{v_{21}}{E_{22}} F_1'' - \frac{1}{4} (y')^2 \right) dy + \int \left(-\frac{4P_i}{E_{22}} F_2 - \frac{v_{21}}{E_{22}} F_2'' - \frac{1}{4} (y')^2 \right) \cos^2 \frac{2\pi x}{eb} dy \quad (14)$$

For v to be constant along the unloaded edges the second part of this equation must be zero. The first part then gives the value of the constant. Hence for constant displacement

$$\int \left(\frac{4P_i}{E_{22}} F_2 + \frac{v_{21}}{E_{22}} F_2'' + \frac{1}{4} (y')^2 \right) dy = 0 \quad (15)$$

The limits for the integration are taken between 0 and $b/2$ and 0 and b . This means effectively that the centre line and side $y = b$ remain parallel to the base line, $y = 0$.

Substituting for F_2 and Y' in equation (15) leads to

$$\frac{2P_i^2}{E_{22}b^2} \int \phi_{mn} dy + \frac{v_{21}P_i}{2E_{22}b^2} \phi'_{mn} \Big|_0^{b, b/2} + \frac{1}{4} \int y'_n y'_m dy = 0 \quad (16)$$

Thus, using equations (12) and (16) the four equations to obtain the constants can be written as follows:

$$L_{1mn} \left(\frac{1}{b} \right) + k_1 C_{2mn} + k_2 C_{4mn} = 0$$

$$2(r-1)$$

$$\sum_{s=0} L_{smn} s \left(\frac{1}{b} \right) + k_1 C_{1mn} \sinh k_1 b + k_1 C_{2mn} \cosh k_1 b$$

$$+ k_2 C_{3mn} \sinh k_2 b + k_2 C_{4mn} \cosh k_2 b = 0$$

$$\frac{2P_i^2}{E_{22}b^2} \left(\sum_{s=0}^{2(r-1)} L_{smn} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{s+1} \frac{b}{s+1} + \frac{C_{1mn}}{k_1} \sinh k_1 \frac{b}{2} + \frac{C_{2mn}}{k_1} \cosh k_1 \frac{b}{2} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{C_{3mn}}{k_2} \sinh k_2 \frac{b}{2} + \frac{C_{4mn}}{k_2} \cosh k_2 \frac{b}{2} - \frac{C_{2mn}}{k_1} - \frac{C_{4mn}}{k_2}) \\
& + \frac{\nu_{21} P_i}{2E_{22} b^2} \sum_{s=0}^{2(r-1)} L_{smn} s \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{s-1} \left(\frac{1}{b}\right) + k_1 C_{1mn} \sinh k_1 \frac{b}{2} + k_1 C_{2mn} \cosh k_1 \frac{b}{2} \\
& + k_2 C_{3mn} \sinh k_2 \frac{b}{2} + k_2 C_{4mn} \cosh k_2 \frac{b}{2} - k_1 C_{2mn} \\
& - k_2 C_{4mn} - \frac{L_{1mn}}{b}) + \frac{1}{4} \int_0^{b/2} (Y_n') (Y_m') dy = 0 \\
& \frac{2P_i^2}{E_{22} b^2} \left(\sum_{s=0}^{2(r-1)} L_{smn} \frac{b}{s+1} + \frac{C_{1mn}}{k_1} \sinh k_1 b + \frac{C_{2mn}}{k_1} \cosh k_1 b \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{C_{3mn}}{k_2} \sinh k_2 b + \frac{C_{4mn}}{k_2} \cosh k_2 b - \frac{C_{2mn}}{k_1} - \frac{C_{4mn}}{k_2} \right) \\
& + \int_0^b (Y_n') (Y_m') dy = 0 \tag{17}
\end{aligned}$$

Note that in the last of the above equations the evaluation of ϕ'_{mn} between 0 and b has been omitted since it is zero from equation (12). This then gives a set of four equations from which the values of the four constants can be obtained directly. One of the standard library routines on the university computer was used to solve the equations for the four unknowns. The stress function F_2 and hence F is thus completely specified.

The Energy Equation

It has been shown (3) that it is only necessary to consider the total strain energy in the buckled plate and that it can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
V = & \frac{a}{4} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N A_n A_m (Q_{nm} - u R_{nm}) \\
& + \frac{ah}{4} \left(\sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N \sum_{p=1}^N \sum_{q=1}^N A_n A_m A_p A_q \frac{\pi^4}{8e^4 b^4} S_{nmpq} + T \right) \tag{18}
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$Q_{nm} = \int_0^b (D_{22} Y_n'' Y_m'' + \frac{\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} D_{11} Y_n Y_m - \frac{2\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} D_{11} \nu_{21} Y_n Y_m)$$

$$+ 4D_{33} \frac{\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} Y_n' Y_m') dy - D_{22} (Y_n'' Y_m') \quad \begin{matrix} y=b \\ y=0 \end{matrix}$$

$$R_{nm} = \int \frac{hE_{11}}{a} \frac{\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} Y_n Y_m dy$$

$$S_{nmpq} = \frac{\pi^4}{8e^4 b^4} \int_0^b (E_{11} Y_n Y_m Y_p Y_q + \frac{2}{b^4} (\frac{1}{E_{11}} \phi_{mn}'' \phi_{pq}'' + \frac{4\pi^2}{e^2 b^2} (\frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} \phi_{mn}'' \phi_{pq}'' + \frac{1}{G_{12}} \phi_{mn}' \phi_{pq}' + \frac{4\pi^2}{e^2 b^2 E_{22}} \phi_{mn} \phi_{pq}))) dy$$

$$T = \int_0^b \frac{2u^2 E_{11}}{a^2} dy \quad (19)$$

A solution to the problem can be obtained by minimising V with respect to each coefficient A_n in turn. The buckling solution can be obtained by eliminating terms involving higher powers from equation (18) and solving the resultant energy equation. This leads to the equation

$$V = \frac{a}{4} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N A_n A_m (Q_{nm} - u R_{nm}) \quad (20)$$

Using a four term buckling solution gives an accurate estimate of the deflected form at buckling which can be used as a basis for a one term post-buckling solution for conditions not much in excess of buckling. In this case the deflected form of the plate after buckling is not permitted to change.

To consider the behaviour further into the postbuckled regime requires additional terms in the postbuckling analysis. For a two term solution a second deflected form has to be assumed. In the following analysis Y_1 the first assumed deflected form for the postbuckling analysis is that obtained from the buckling solution.

Since it is known that the plate tends to 'flatten' out at the centre as the post buckling range is increased, the second deflected form is chosen with this in mind.

It is obtained from the four term buckling solution by ensuring that the deflection at the centre is zero. In addition the slope at the centre is made zero also thus ensuring a form which is symmetrical at the centre of the plate. Since this deflected form is based on that obtained from the buckling solution, all the boundary conditions associated with the buckling analysis are satisfied for this new deflected form.

Introducing the limits the energy expression now requiring minimisation becomes

$$V = \frac{a}{4} \sum_{n=1}^2 \sum_{m=1}^2 A_n A_m (Q_{nm} - u R_{nm}) + \frac{ah}{4} \left(\sum_{n=1}^2 \sum_{m=1}^2 \sum_{p=1}^2 \sum_{q=1}^2 A_n A_m A_p A_q \frac{P_i^2}{8} S_{nmpq} + T \right) \quad (21)$$

where the ϕ_{mn} etc in the expression for S_{nmpq} are obtained as indicated earlier. This equation was minimised using a standard routine on the university computer to obtain the appropriate values of A_1 and A_2 .

It is now possible to obtain expressions for the total in plane load in the plate and the membrane and bending stresses, from a consideration of the basic equations. The total in plane load is given by

$$P_{in} = \frac{hE_{11}b}{a} u - \frac{hE_{11}P_i}{4} \int_0^b \sum_{n=1}^2 (A_n Y_n)^2 dy \quad (22)$$

The membrane stresses are found as before and given by

$$\sigma_x^m = \frac{E_{11}P_i}{4} \sum_{n=1}^2 (A_n Y_n)^2 - \frac{uE_{11}}{a} + \frac{P_i}{2b^2} \sum_{n=1}^2 \sum_{m=1}^2 A_n A_m \phi_{mn}'' \cos \frac{2\pi x}{eb} \quad (23)$$

$$\sigma_y^m = -\frac{2P_i^2}{b^2} \sum_{n=1}^2 \sum_{m=1}^2 A_n A_m \phi_{mn} \cos \frac{2\pi x}{eb} \quad (24)$$

The shear stress is given by

$$\tau_{xy} = -\frac{\pi^3}{e^3 b^5} \sum_{n=1}^2 \sum_{m=1}^2 A_n A_m \phi_{mn}' \sin \frac{2\pi x}{eb} \quad (25)$$

The bending stresses are found to be

$$\sigma_x^b = \frac{6D_{11}}{h^2} (P_i \sum_{n=1}^2 A_n Y_n - v_{21} \sum_{n=1}^2 A_n Y_n'') \cos \frac{\pi x}{eb} \quad (26)$$

$$\sigma_y^b = \frac{6D_{22}}{h^2} (-\sum_{n=1}^2 A_n Y_n'' + P_i v_{12} \sum_{n=1}^2 A_n Y_n) \cos \frac{\pi x}{eb} \quad (27)$$

The stresses and deflections in the plate in the postbuckling range for the two term solution have thus been obtained.

Orthotropic Panels with Initial Imperfections

In the previous theoretical work the plates have been assumed to be perfectly flat. Since it is impossible to manufacture perfectly flat plates all structural elements of plate form will have some degree of imperfection and this should be accounted for.

A number of researchers have examined the problem for both isotropic plates (4), and orthotropic plates (5). It has been found that the effects of initial imperfections are most marked around the local buckling load and most detrimental to plate load carrying capacity if they are similar in form to the deflections due to local buckling. This both facilitates the analysis and means that the results obtained, by considering the deflections to be of the same form as the local buckles, are conservative. In the present consideration, the method used by Rhodes et al (4) for isotropic plates is extended to cover the orthotropic system.

The plate considered is shown in Figure 2 with initial imperfections w_0 and total deflection w . For the initially imperfect plate the new equation

Fig. 2- Co-ordinate system and convention for imperfect plate

linking the stress function and the deflection function becomes

$$\frac{1}{E_{22}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^4} + H \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{1}{E_{11}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial y^4}$$

$$= \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right) - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} - \left(\left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x \partial y} \right) - \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (28)$$

Since the effect of imperfections is most marked around the critical buckling load it is sufficient to consider a one term solution. The deflection function can thus be taken in the form

$$w = \bar{A} \bar{Y} \cos \frac{\pi x}{eb} \quad (29)$$

and if w_0 is assumed to be of the same form it can be taken as

$$w_0 = \bar{A}_0 \bar{Y} \cos \frac{\pi x}{eb} \quad (30)$$

As before the corresponding stress function can be found by substituting in equation (2) which leads to a solution for the stress function F_1 and F_2 of equation (7) in the form

$$F_1'' = -\frac{uE_{11}}{a} + \frac{E_{11}\pi^2}{4e^2b^2} (\bar{A}^2 - \bar{A}_0^2) \bar{Y}^2 \quad (31)$$

and

$$F_2 = \frac{\pi^2}{2e^2b^4} (\bar{A}^2 - \bar{A}_0^2) \bar{\phi}(y) \quad (32)$$

The strain energy stored in the plate can be obtained by incorporating the effect of \bar{A}_0 into the expressions for the perfect plate giving

$$V = \frac{a}{4} ((\bar{A} - \bar{A}_0)^2 Q - u(\bar{A}^2 - \bar{A}_0^2)R) + \frac{ah}{4} ((\bar{A}^2 - \bar{A}_0^2)^2 S + T) \quad (33)$$

If \bar{A}_0 is set to zero then the one term solution for the perfect plate is obtained. To obtain the required relationship between \bar{A} and u the strain energy expression is minimised with respect to \bar{A} yielding after rearrangement

$$u = \left(\frac{\bar{A} - \bar{A}_0}{\bar{A}} \right) \frac{Q}{R} + \frac{2hS}{R} (\bar{A}^2 - \bar{A}_0^2) \quad (34)$$

Thus for any prescribed value of \bar{A} the value of u can be obtained provided the value of the initial deflection coefficient \bar{A}_0 is known. The relation between u and the applied load can be found as before giving

$$P_{in} = h \int_0^b \sigma_x dx = -\frac{hE_{11}b}{a} \left(\frac{\bar{A} - \bar{A}_0}{\bar{A}} \right) \frac{Q}{R} + (\bar{A}^2 - \bar{A}_0^2) \left(\frac{E_{11}\pi^2 h}{4e^2b^2} \bar{Y} \int_0^b dy - \frac{2h^2E_{11}b}{a} \frac{S}{R} \right) \quad (35)$$

The membrane stress at any point in the plate can be obtained from the basic equations as before

$$\sigma_x^m = -\frac{uE_{11}}{a} + (\bar{A}^2 - \bar{A}_0^2) \left(\frac{E_{11}\pi^2}{4e^2b^2} \bar{Y} + \frac{\pi^2}{2e^2b^4} \bar{\phi}'' \cos \frac{2\pi x}{eb} \right)$$

$$\sigma_y^m = -(\bar{A}^2 - \bar{A}_0^2) \frac{\pi^2}{2e^2b^4} \bar{\phi} \left(\frac{2\pi}{eb}\right) \cos \frac{2\pi x}{eb} \quad (36)$$

Similarly the bending stresses can be obtained in the usual way giving

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x^b &= \pm \frac{6M_x}{h^2} = \pm \frac{6D_{11}}{h^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2(w - w_0)}{\partial x^2} + \nu_{21} \frac{\partial^2(w - w_0)}{\partial y^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{6D_{11}}{h^2} (\bar{A} - \bar{A}_0) \left(-\bar{Y} \frac{\pi^2}{e^2b^2} + \nu_{21} \bar{Y}'' \right) \cos \frac{\pi x}{eb} \\ \sigma_y^b &= \frac{6D_{22}}{h^2} (\bar{A} - \bar{A}_0) (\bar{Y}'' - \nu_{12} \frac{\pi^2}{e^2b^2} \bar{Y}) \cos \frac{\pi x}{eb} \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

Thus the behaviour of the imperfect orthotropic plate can be completely obtained by specifying the deflection coefficient \bar{A} and using the relevant equations to obtain the deflections or stresses. The results presented are for stress free unloaded edges.

Application of Results to Specific Case

The above analyses have been applied to a representative orthotropic panel in the form of a glass reinforced plastic (GRP) plate. Typical values for this plate are $E_{11} = 30 \text{ GN/m}^2$, $E_{22} = 6 \text{ GN/m}^2$, $G_{12} = 5 \text{ GN/m}^2$ and $\nu_{12} = 0.33$. Results for the stress free unloaded edges are first presented followed by those where the unloaded edges are held straight. The effects of initial imperfection are then briefly discussed.

Stress Free Unloaded Edges

The effect of the two term solution on the load-end displacement curve can be seen from Fig 3. It is evident that a one term solution is

Fig. 3 - Load-end displacement curves for square SS GRP plates

sufficiently accurate at a P/P_{cr} of 1.5 and perhaps as high as 2.0. The effect on the load-out of plane deflection is seen in Fig 4 for various

Fig. 4 - Effect of aspect ratio on post buckling deflections for SS GRP plates

aspect ratios for the plate with the unloaded edges simply supported. A similar trend is noted where the unloaded edges are fixed. It has been assumed that the plate would buckle into one half wave in the x direction in each case.

Post critical stress distributions are plotted in Fig 5 for both the one

Fig. 5 - Membrane and bending stresses in square GRP SS plate

term and two term solutions. The results are for simply supported plates 0.25 m square and 0.0025 m thick.

In all, five different stresses are presented. Both the membrane stresses and the bending stresses at the centre are given together with the membrane stress at the mid point of the unloaded edges. This latter stress is the largest membrane value in the plate. In reinforced plastics, however, it is not necessarily the most significant because of the low strength in the transverse direction. Indeed, because of this low strength, the transverse bending stress σ_y^b may in some cases become the most important value.

It can be seen that the largest stress at the centre, as expected, is the bending stress in the longitudinal direction. The membrane stress accompanying this can in some cases change from compression to tension as the post-buckling range is increased. There is usually, however, adequate strength in this direction to account for these large values.

On the other hand the stresses in the transverse direction do not at first appear significant. When it is remembered, however, that the transverse strength is very small compared to the longitudinal values, these stresses become relatively important. As seen from the figures the membrane stress in this direction σ_y^m is always positive with the two term solution having little effect on its value. When the effect of the bending stress σ_y^b is added to this (remembering that σ_y^b is positive in the extreme fibre on one side of the plate and negative in the extreme fibre on the other) the net value can then approach the ultimate strength of the plate in this direction. For this stress the two term solution has a significant effect. As can be seen, for example from Figure 5, the value is substantially reduced at the centre. However, as will be shown later (see Figure 7) the value can be increased quite significantly towards the edge as the deflected form alters and 'flattens' at the centre. This means that the critical area for failure approaches the unloaded edges of the plate as the post-buckling range is increased. This observation was confirmed by experiments.

Stress distributions across the plate at approximately twice the critical load are presented in Figures 6 and 7. The curves follow the usual trend with a high membrane value at the supported edges. The effect of the two term solution on the membrane stresses is seen from Figure 6 to be most marked at the edges and the centre of the plate. In the case of the bending stresses shown in Figure 7 the extra term is seen to have a marked effect on the bending stress in the y direction. The maximum value is seen to move away from the centre and towards the edge. Since the tensile strength in this direction is only of the order of 20 MN/m this is evidently going to be a significant increase.

Unloaded Edges Held Straight

The results of the above analysis are first validated by comparison with results in the literature for the same boundary conditions. Harris (6) presented an exact solution for the relative stiffness at buckling for plates with the membrane boundary conditions considered here. Applying his equation to the GRP plate gives a relative stiffness at buckling of 0.375. Using the present analysis a value of 0.374888 was obtained. Since the present method gives an upper bound on the stresses the very small difference is evidently due to mathematical inaccuracies within the computer. Similar relatively close values were obtained for the other plates considered earlier and hence gave confidence in the analysis.

Fig. 6 - Membrane stress distributions in symmetrical half of square SS GRP plate

Fig. 7 - Bending stress distributions in symmetrical half of square SS GRP plate

The analysis was also applied to the post-buckling results presented in(7). Plate E from this paper was chosen as a basis for comparison since its properties were nearest to those obtaining in the GRP plate to which the present results are applied. The load-end displacement curve obtained for the square plate matched exactly that given in the paper. The same was true for the effective width curve.

The large deflection behaviour is presented in Figures 8 and 9 from which

Fig. 8 - Load-end displacement curves for square GRP plate

Fig. 9 - Relation between post-buckling load and out of plane deflection for square SS GRP plate

it is seen that the two term solution does not give such a marked difference as noted earlier for the stress free edges. The relative stiffness after buckling remains almost constant.

The distribution of stress across the plate is given in Figures 10 and 11 for the case of P/P_{cr} having a value of 2.07. The multi-term solution

Fig. 10 - Membrane stress distribution across symmetric half of square SS GRP plate

Fig. 11 - Distribution of bending stress in symmetrical half of square SS GRP plate

is seen to have a marked effect on the membrane stress value at the unloaded edge. The one term solution gives a constant value of stress along the length of the plate. The two term solution shows that the value is increased by around 20% at the buckle crest while it is reduced by around 13% at the buckle node.

The Effects of Alternative Membrane Boundary Conditions on the Unloaded Edges

In this section comparison is made between the two unloaded edge membrane boundary conditions considered, viz stress free edges and edges held straight. Figures 12 and 13 present the large deflection behaviour while Figure 14 presents the most significant stress comparison.

Fig. 12 - Comparison of load-end displacement curves for two unloaded edge conditions

Fig. 13 - Effect of membrane edge conditions on out of plane deflections

Fig. 14 - Effect of membrane edge conditions on membrane stresses for square SS GRP plate

It can be seen that the plate with the unloaded edges held straight has greater stiffness, smaller deflections, and smaller stresses at the mid point of the unloaded edge than the plate with stress free unloaded edges, although in some cases the differences are not significant. In addition the transverse bending stress has a maximum value at the centre and therefore its position is predictable. In the case of the stress free edges its position varied as the postbuckling range was increased. This makes it more difficult to predict the location of possible collapse. It is evident therefore that a plate with the unloaded edges held straight is to be preferred. Fortunately these are often the conditions met with in structural applications, where GRP and composite materials in general have a potential application.

Plates with Initial Imperfections

The effect of initial imperfection on load-end displacement behaviour is shown in Figure 15. As can be seen, the effect of the imperfections is most

Fig. 15 - Load-end displacement curves for square SS GRP plates for various initial imperfections

marked around the buckling load of the plate. A similar set of results to this figure is obtained by plotting the post-buckling load against the maximum membrane stress in the plate. It is thus evident that while the magnitude of the stresses is significantly affected around the buckling load, they are virtually unaffected at the higher loads.

The same relative effect is observed for the out of plane deflections presented in Figure 16.

Fig. 16 - Relationship between post-buckling load and central deflection for square SS GRP plate with various imperfections

Conclusions

The paper has outlined the large deflection and post-buckling behaviour of orthotropic plates subjected to uniform in plane loading and having various boundary conditions on the unloaded edges. The effect of initial imperfections has also been discussed. Provided large deflections can be tolerated and the reduction in stiffness at buckling accounted for, there should be further applications for the orthotropic plate as a particular class of composite construction. The ability to predict what happens at buckling is in itself of value to designers.

Notation

A_n	Coefficients in deflection series
$\bar{A} \quad \bar{A}_0$	Coefficient in deflection series for one term post-buckling analysis for perfect and imperfect plate respectively
a b	Panel dimensions in x and y directions respectively
$D_{11} \quad D_{22}$	Flexural rigidity of plate per unit width for bending about the y and x axes respectively, given by $D_{11} = E_{11}h^3/12(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})$ and $D_{22} = E_{22}h^3/12(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})$

$D_{12} D_{21}$	Cross flexural rigidity of plate per unit width (= $\nu_{21} D_{11} = \nu_{12} D_{22}$)
D_{33}	Twisting rigidity of plate about x and y axes given by $D_{33} = Gh^3/12$
D_3	Given by $D_{12} + 2D_{33}$
$E_{11} E_{22}$	Modulus of elasticity in the x and y directions respectively
e	Ratio of buckle half wave length to plate width
F	Airy stress function, defined in text
G_{12}	Elastic shear modulus in x-y plane
H	Defined as $(1/G_{12} - 2\nu_{12}/E_{11})$
h	Plate thickness
$m n p q$	Integer counters
$P_{in} P_{cr}$	Applied load and critical load respectively in x direction
P_i	Defined as π^2/e^2b^2
$u v$	In-plane displacements, of the plate middle surface, in the x and y directions respectively
u_{cr}	In-plane displacement in the x direction at buckling
w	Out of plane deflections of the plate
V	Total strain energy
$Y(y)$	Deflections across buckled plate
$\sigma_x^m \sigma_y^m$	Direct membrane stresses in the x and y directions respectively
$\sigma_x^b \sigma_y^b$	Bending stresses in the x and y directions respectively
σ_y^{ult}	Ultimate tensile strength in y direction
τ_{xy}	Shear stress in the x-y plane
$\phi_{mn}(y)$	Used in stress function F_2 (equation 9)
$\nu_{12} \nu_{21}$	Poisson's ratio in the x and y directions respectively
Primes	Denote differentiation in the y direction e.g. $F'' = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2}$

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